

Effect of γ -radiation on thermal and photoluminescence properties of 2D layered zinc phosphate $[\text{H}_3\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_3]^+[\text{Zn}_2(\text{HPO}_4)_3]$

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Abstract : Effect of ^{60}Co γ -radiation (5 and 300 kGy) on thermal stability and photoluminescence properties of 2D layered zinc phosphate $[\text{H}_3\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_3]^+[\text{Zn}_2(\text{HPO}_4)_3]$ (ZnP) has been investigated. X-Ray diffraction pattern reveals that γ -irradiation did not cause any stress on the crystal structure of ZnP and it was thermally stable up to 400 °C. The photoluminescence spectrum of complex ZnP displays a characteristic broad emission peak at 420 nm on photoexcitation at 365 nm. The photoluminescence emission properties had been examined after γ -irradiation at 5 and 300 kGy radiation doses.

Keywords : Zinc phosphate, photoluminescence, thermal stability, γ -radiation.

Introduction

Open framework structures of metal phosphates are of great importance not only due to their rich structural chemistry but also due to their wide applications in various fields ranging from traditional ion exchange, gas sorption and heterogeneous catalysis to modern microelectronics and medical diagnosis¹⁻⁵. Photoluminescence (PL) is one of the important property for lighting-element-free open-framework phosphates⁶⁻⁹, and coordination complexes¹⁰. On the other hand, induced γ -irradiation on phosphors and complexes are of current interest in recent years because of its wide range of applications in various fields like medical imaging, industrial process, optical communications, lasers, fluorescent lamps, light emitting diodes etc.¹¹⁻¹³. High energy ionizing radiation (X-rays, γ -rays) produce ionization results in partial displacement depending upon the energy of radiation^{14,15}. Herein, we report influence of γ -radiation on thermal stability and photoluminescence (PL) study of 2D layered zinc phosphate $[\text{H}_3\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_3]^+[\text{Zn}_2(\text{HPO}_4)_3]$ (ZnP).

Results and discussion

The molecular structure of complex ZnP is shown in the Fig. 1. The 2D structure is built with the networking of ZnO_4 , HPO_4 tetrahedral units. The vertex linkage be-

tween these units creates an anionic frame work of formula $[\text{Zn}_2(\text{HPO}_4)_3]^{2-}$ and charge compensation is achieved by the protonated amine of 1,3-diaminopropane $[\text{C}_6\text{HN}]^{2+}$. The 2D layers are formed between the 4- and 12-ring sheets running along [100] (Fig. 1b and Fig. 1c). In ZnO_4 tetrahedra, the Zn-O bond distances are in the range of 1.902–1.989 Å and P-O distances in the range of 1.506–1.571 Å. The larger distances of 1.582–1.571 Å indicates protonated $\text{PO}_4(\text{HPO}_4)$ units. The organic amines interact with the inorganic hosts by means of strong network of H-bonding ($\text{N}\cdots\text{O}$: 2.769–3.060 Å).

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of ZnP : (a) 2D framework, (b) 12-ring channels and (c) 4-ring channels.

Effect of γ -radiation on crystal structure :

The FT-IR spectrum of ZnP complex before and after γ -irradiation is shown in Fig. 2. A broad peak at 3440 cm^{-1} is due to O-H stretching vibrations crystal water. Peaks at 1115 cm^{-1} , 906 cm^{-1} are due to the P=O and M-O-P stretching vibrations, respectively. It is observed that the intensity of bands progressively increased on increasing the γ -irradiation from 5 to 300 kGy without any change in the band position. The above results confirms that there is no change in the crystal structure of ZnP after γ -irradiation upto 300 kGy.

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectrum of ZnP : (a) before γ -irradiation, (b) γ -irradiated at 5 kGy and (c) γ -irradiated at 300 kGy.

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of ZnP before and after γ -irradiation are shown in Fig. 3. In general, γ -irradiation might cause a prominent change in the positions of atoms in the crystal lattice. It was observed that γ -irradiation did not cause any change in peak positions except little change in intensity of peaks. So γ -irradiation did not influence the crystal structure of ZnP even at high doses.

Fig. 3. Powder XRD patterns of ZnP : (a) before γ -irradiation, (b) γ -irradiated at 5 kGy and (c) γ -irradiated at 300 kGy.

Effect of γ -radiation on thermal stability :

The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of ZnP carried out under nitrogen atmosphere is presented in Fig. 4. The compound is thermally stable up to 300 °C. TGA of ZnP exhibits three weight loss steps. The first mass loss of 7.0% between 120–150 °C corresponds to the loss of lattice water molecules. The second weight loss of 11.9% between 280–300 °C corresponds to the loss of template amine molecules. The third weight of 23.2% between 300–450 °C corresponds to decomposition of inorganic framework.

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric analysis of ZnP : (a) before γ -irradiation and (b) γ -irradiated at 300 kGy.

In general, γ -irradiation may produce chemical damage, lattice defects and atomic or ionic imperfections in crystalline materials. Moreover, the lattice defects introduced by ionizing radiation does not influence the thermal stability of material unless it was a chemical damage. The mass loss pattern up to 300 °C is almost similar in both pre and post γ -irradiated samples at 300 kGy (Fig. 4b). While, the decomposition temperature was found to be lower in post irradiated sample probably due to breaking of hydrogen bonds associated with inorganic framework and template amine molecules.

Effect of γ -radiation on photoluminescence :

The photoluminescence (PL) spectra of ZnP before and after γ -irradiation is depicted in Fig. 5. On photoexcitation at 365 nm, ZnP exhibit an emission peak at 420 nm (blue emission). According to previous reports from Wang^{8,17} on blue and yellow luminescent micro porous metal phosphates, template residing in nano/micro

Fig. 5. Photoluminescence spectra of ZnP : (a) before γ -irradiation, (b) γ -irradiated at 5 kGy and (c) γ -irradiated at 300 kGy.

sized channels or pores of ZnPO_4 acts as good sensitizer. Furthermore, these emissions might have probably arisen from $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of 1,3-diaminopropane.

ZnP was exposed to γ -irradiation at doses of 5 and 300 kGy. In general, γ -irradiation cause some lattice defects in the crystalline sites of solid materials. However, in ZnP ionization radiation does not affect the shape and wave length of the photoluminescence adequately indicating excellent resistance of the metal phosphates. In addition, γ -irradiation influence the reduction of photoluminescence intensity. This quenching of intensity could be due to non-radiative emission.

Materials and methods :

AR grade zinc acetate dihydrate $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) were purchased from Merck-India. 1,3-Diamino propane was procured from Sigma-Aldrich. ZnP was prepared hydrothermally by known procedure reported by Alejandra *et al.*¹⁶. Elemental analysis calculated (%) for $\text{C}_3\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_{12}\text{P}_3\text{Zn}_2$ (ZnP) : C, 7.32; N, 4.62; H, 2.88. Found : C, 7.28; N, 4.403; H, 2.78.

The IR spectrum was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer "Spectrum Two" FT-IR spectrophotometer using KBr pellet method in the $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ wave number range at room temperature. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern was recorded on "PANALYTICAL XPertpro Powder X-ray diffractometer" with graphite monochromatic CuK_α ($\lambda = 1.5406\text{ \AA}$) radiation at room temperature.

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was performed using "Melter Toledo TGA/DSC-1" apparatus in a temperature range between 30 and 1000 $^\circ\text{C}$ under nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The C, H and N microanalysis was carried out using "Thermo Scientific FLASH-2000" elemental analyzer. Luminescence spectrum of the solid sample was recorded on "Perkin-Elmer LS-55 Luminescence Spectrometer" at room temperature. γ -irradiation studies were performed at room temperature by using ^{60}Co gamma cell (^{60}Co - source capacity 3700 Ci) at a dose rate of 2.95 kGy/h. The pure dry sample of complex ZnP was irradiated at 5 and 300 kGy.

Conclusions

2D layered zinc phosphate, $[\text{H}_3\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_3] \cdot [\text{Zn}_2(\text{HPO}_4)_3]$, was prepared according to the reported procedure and the γ -radiation effects on thermal stability and photoluminescence properties was examined. The above investigation results indicated that ZnP was highly stable up to 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ even after γ -irradiation at 300 kGy. Further, photoluminescence decreased without change in wavelength due to non-radiative emission. This kind of study is very useful for optoelectronic applications.

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